

Sorption of Strong Electrolytes on Ion-exchange Resins : Separation of Binary Mixtures of Some Strong Acids

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The sorption of naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid, sulphuric acid, and hydrochloric acid in dilute aqueous solution on monofunctional carboxylic acid cation-exchange resins has been applied for the separation of binary mixtures of the first with the other two.

Sorption of strong electrolytes by ion-exchange resins due to the Donnan membrane effect has been studied by several workers¹⁻¹⁰. If the sorption can be significantly different, due to the differences in activity coefficients, it may be feasible to separate two strong electrolytes in a binary mixture. With this object in view, a study was undertaken to attempt separation of naphthalene-2-sulphonic (NF) acid from sulphuric acid and hydrochloric acid. Separation of naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid from sulphuric acid has been reported by using other methods¹¹⁻¹⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL

Naphthalene-2-sulphonic (NF) acid was prepared and purified as recommended by Vogel¹⁶ and Witt¹⁷. H₂SO₄, HCl, and NaOH of A. R. quality and distilled water were used.

The resins used were from samples of Zeo-Carb-226 type (Permutit Co., London) monofunctional carboxylic acid cation-exchange resins of relative degree of cross-linking (% nominal divinylbenzene content), X=2.5, 6.11, and 16 (hereafter referred to as resins

1. Juda *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 3736.
2. Pepper *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3129.
3. Argersinger and Davidson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 92.
4. Gregor and Gottlich, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 3539.
5. Kraus and Moore, *ibid.*, 1953, **75**, 1457.
6. Gottlich and Gregor, *ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 4639.
7. Thomas and Diamond, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 2021.
8. Freeman, *ibid.*, 1960, **64**, 1049.
9. Tye, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4784.
10. Shone, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, **58**, 805.
11. Dennis, B. P. 109, 709/1916; Swiss Pat. 75,550/1916; U. S. P. 1, 228, 414/1917; Can. Pat. 177, 140; U.S.P. 1, 332, 203/1920.
12. Othmer *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1943, **35**, 326.
13. Ito and Migana, *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, **55**, 8179d.
14. Glogan *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1961, **53**, 275.
15. Anderson *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1955, **47**, 1620.
16. "Practical Organic Chemistry", London, 1948, p. 531.
17. *Chem. Abs.*, 1915, **9**, 2094.

Cx-2.5, Cx-6, Cx-11, and Cx-16) and Amberlite IRC-50 (Rohm and Haas Co.) (hereafter referred to as resin Cx-8, as its X is considered to be close to 8). The resins were washed, conditioned, regenerated, and moisture content and capacity estimated¹⁸.

Estimations of Acids.—Fig. 1 shows the UV absorption spectrum of NF acid^{19,20} in dilute aqueous solution, using Beckman model DU spectrophotometer with 10-mm quartz cells. Presence of H_2SO_4 or HCl up to $10^{-2}M/l$ had no observable effect on the UV absorption of NF acid in aqueous solution. Hence in binary mixtures, NF acid was estimated by absorption at 274 $m\mu$ and the total acids were estimated by titration against a standard NaOH solution. Thus the composition of binary mixtures in samples could be estimated.

FIG. 1. UV spectrum of NF acid in aq. soln.

Procedure.—Columns were set up for each resin. Table I records the column data. A solution of NF acid (*ca.* 0.05*N*) was passed through the column and samples were collected and estimated for acid sorbed. The run was continued till there was no further sorption and the total amount of acid sorbed was calculated. The column was then washed free of acid with distilled water and the run was repeated with H_2SO_4 (*c.* 0.05*N*) and HCl (*c.* 0.05*N*).

18. Bafna and Govindan, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1956, **48**, 310.

19. Litloff, *Chem. Abs.*, 1929, **23**, 3404.

20. Daghish, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4859.

The amounts of H_2SO_4 and HCl sorbed in such runs were essentially the same. Table I records the data obtained. It was observed that while the quantity of acid sorbed per equivalent of resin decreased as X increased, the ratio, r , given by $\{NF \text{ acid sorbed per equivalent of resin}/H_2SO_4 \text{ (or } HCl) \text{ sorbed per equivalent of resin}\}$ was found to increase, reach a maximum, and then decrease with the increase in X .

TABLE I

Resin	..	..	Cx-2.5	Cx-6	Cx-8	Cx-11	Cx-16
X	..	..	2.5	6	8	11	16
Moisture content (%) of air-dry resin	..	..	23.4	20.9	15.6	17.0	12.0
Capacity (m.e. per g. oven-dry resin)	..	..	10.60	9.77	10.40	8.70	6.84
Column capacity (capacity of resin in column in m.e.)	..	..	67.95	95.66	87.75	115.30	112.00
Mesh size of the resin	..	..	-20+30	-60+100	-40+60	-60+100	-60+100
Bed length (cm)	..	..	60.0	54.5	44.0	50.8	53.0
Bed volume (ml)	..	..	31.5	29.3	23.5	27.0	27.9
Flow rate (ml/min.)	..	..	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Acid sorbed (m.e./per equiv. of resin)	}	NF acid (a)	16.250	11.430	8.439	5.631	3.100
		H_2SO_4 (b)	10.820	5.896	4.210	3.122	3.080
		HCl (c)	10.850	5.899	4.190	3.119	3.100
Ratio, r , given by	}	a/b	1.502	1.939	2.004	1.803	1.007
		a/c	1.496	1.937	2.014	1.805	1.000

FIG. 2. Elution curves with resin Cx-6 for acids.
A-NF acid; B-HCl; C- H_2SO_4 .

Next, a column of resin Cx-6 was set up. The column data were: column capacity, 310.1 m.e; bed volume, 102.4 ml; bed length, 43 cm; flow rate, 1 ml/min.; 20 ml of NF acid (0.0525N) was sorbed on the resin column and then eluted with distilled water till free

of acid. The procedure was then repeated with H_2SO_4 (0.0520*N*) and HCl (0.05093*N*).

FIG. 3. Separation of NF acid (A) and HCl (B) with resin Cx-6. 20 ml of acid solution consisting of 10 ml of 0.05093*N*- HCl and 10 ml of 0.05216*N*-NF acid was sorbed.

FIG. 4. Separation of NF acid (A) and H_2SO_4 (C) with resin Cx-6. 20 ml of acid solution containing 10 ml of 0.0525*N*-NF acid and 10 ml of 0.0525*N*- H_2SO_4 was sorbed.

Fig. 2 shows the separate elution curves for the three acids obtained in this way. While elution of the later portions is relatively slow and the later part of the elution curve trails along volume axis, the break through volume for NF acid has been found significantly different from that for the other two acids. Next, different binary mixtures of NF acid with HCl and H_2SO_4 were sorbed and eluted similarly. Fig. 3 and 4 illustrate the separations achieved.